

Data transmission as musical performance

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores how patterns found within the field of data transmission could be conceived of as musical phrases that can be performed by voice and translated by computers back into information. It is based on practice-based research, and the presentation of hardware and software to audiences within a performance.

I provide an overview of the relevance of this work within the fields of sonification and musical human-computer-interaction, and continue to describe the software and hardware I have developed to convert sound to data.

I describe how learning traditional musical systems that employ rhythmic improvisation such as flamenco, Cuban rumba, bata and Indian Konnakol could be useful in thinking about how computer signals can be explored musically.

I conclude with reflections on performing with this system and thoughts for extending these ideas further towards multiple performers.

1. LISTENING TO INFORMATION

In a book of essays called *Postdigital Aesthetics*, the artist and thinker Shintaro Miyazaki argues that the signals that transmit information and form the basis for our digital world should be analysed by the “ears, the hands and the whole body” [1]. He cites a number of fascinating examples where listening to machines was crucial to working with them, This includes Ferranti engineers who in the 1950’s ran custom programs on the computers specifically to listen to faults in the machines.

The increase of speed and reduction of scale of computers has made the sounds that they produce harder to perceive. Artists including Christina Kubisch, Martin Hause and Shintaro Miyazaki have used electromagnetic transducers to convert signals that carry information through the air into sound. While these works allow us to perceive quali-

ties of location and strength of signals, they do not help us understand the logic of digital signals.

The difficulties of perceiving information within sound has been widely discussed by both theorists within the fields of sonification and musicology. In their essay *Theory of sonification*, Walker and Nees state that ‘major limiting factors in the deployment of sonifications have been, and will continue to be, the perceptual and information processing capabilities of the human listener.’ [2]

Within the European classical music tradition encoding layers of meaning into sound has been popular at least since the 17th century. The composer Johann Sebastian Bach famously encoded his name into his works of music using note letters to represent textual letters. These types of musical cryptograms have continued to be explored by many composers including Messiaen who encoded a dizzying amount of information in his work *Méditations*. This work contains no lyrics but is so densely fully of information the organist Andrew Shenton has dedicated a book analysing it and decoding it. The music contains numerous devices including a “musical alphabet in which a rhythmicized pitch is assigned to each letter of the roman alphabet.”[3]

To understand the information within Messiaen’s work is undoubtedly well beyond the perceptual and information processing capabilities of most people but as suggested by Shenton it is “worth studying in depth because of its intrinsic interest as a musical technique”. [3] Shenton quotes Messiaen who alludes to more abstract notions of language and translation.

“The different languages known to us are, above all, a means of communication. They are generally vocal in character, but is that the only medium for transmission? One can very well imagine a language based on movement, images, colours or smells, and everyone knows that the Braille alphabet uses touch. In each case one begins with the established convention: it is agreed that *this* means *that*.”

We can also find examples of music where information is fully intended to be transmitted and understood and not hidden. This is well described in the book *Talking Drums of Africa* by John Carrington who in 1939 learnt the language of the Kele people of the then Belgian Congo and documented the similarity between the drum rhythms and the spoken language giving a beautiful account of the

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types of messages sent and the ingenious ways of encoding them. [4] Amanda Villepastour has also documented the language encoded in Yorùbá bàtá drumming in her book Ancient text messages of the Yorùbá bàtá drum. Here she describes how the language is encoded into drumming patterns and how it is now a dying art due to the decreasing amount of people who understand the Yorùbá language and how players have gravitated to playing danceable rhythms as opposed to more free flowing text. [5]

2. SLOWING DOWN DATA TRANSMISSION

The aim of the technology and performances I have developed is to provide the audience and performer with a sense of the particular rhythmic patterns that are used in data communications. Information that is usually invisibly transferred at high speed through wires or electromagnetic waves is slowed down and translated to the sonic spectrum. I invite audiences to engage with how machines communicate, the materiality of data, and to explore the musical and performative potential of reenacting these processes and the mechanical limits of the human performance.

The work has developed from an interest in exploring a critical approach to working with technology. Amidst the increasing growth of apps, software and instruments that aim to make digital music-making easy, this work provokes the performer to make sounds and rhythms according to the logic of computing, to become machine-like. Or to requote Miyazaki to analyse digital systems with our “ears, the hands and the whole body” [1]

I would also align this project with the framework developed by Anthony Dunne in *Herzian Tales* and suggest that the software developed could be considered a post-optimal object, this is something that Dunne describes as;

“The design of conceptual electronic products as a way of provoking complex and meaningful reflection on the ubiquitous, dematerializing, and intelligent artificial environment we inhabit” [6]

3. SOFTWARE TO CONVERT SOUND TO DATA

There are numerous forms of data communications that could be used as a basis for this work, and to describe them and their histories would be relevant but beyond the scope of this paper. Here I will focus on the transmission of ASCII text using a popular form of asynchronous serial communication commonly used between computers.

It has become convention within the world of computer programming to start by printing the phrase “hello world”

to a display. Lets begin by focusing on the serial transmission of the letter h.

Figure 1 shows a plot of the letter h that was recorded as an audio signal from a micro-controller programmed to send the letter h. It demonstrates how each letter is sent as voltage moving between 0 and 5 Volts. As illustrated these transitions are interpreted by another machine as either 0s or 1s. A total of 10 bits are required to send each letter. The first bit known as the start bit is always a 0 and the last bit known as a stop bit is always a 1. The 8 bits between contain the binary information for the letter h.

Figure 1. Plot of the serial transmission of the letter h

To mimic this pattern with the human voice requires some form of translation. We could choose amplitude modulation or frequency modulation to move between the two states. For this piece I chose amplitude modulation to act as an equivalent of voltage and made the decision that a loud sound would equate to a 1 and silence a 0.

Figure 2. Plot of the serial transmission of the letter h using amplitude modulation of the human voice..

Software was developed in OpenFrameworks to mimic a serial connection. To avoid the use of additional libraries a simple amplitude detection algorithm was used to the

follow amplitude of the signal. The software runs to a click track and between each click it checks to see if the sound is above or below a given threshold. If it is above it is above a given threshold it displays a 1 and if below a 0. At the end of each byte of information the software checks that the start bit was 0 and the stop bit was 1 and then outputs the byte as a displayed ASCII character.

Like a machine, the performer has to work hard to keep sounds short and precise enough to not to trigger unwanted 1s or 0s.

4. MUSICAL PHRASING AND LEARNING TO IMPROVISE IN SERIAL

To consider these ten bits within a musical context we could think of them as a group of 10 notes or rests, and to make this easier to work with we could subdivide them into quavers and have a bar of 5/4 as shown in Figure 3..

Figure 3. Score of the serial transmission of the letter h as musical notes.

My first explorations with the system involved transcribing the ASCII table into this notated form and then trying to perform them.

This way of performing with the system works well and is close to the composer and musician relation found in western classical music. However, I am interested in developing ways of learning these binary sequences in ways that allows for greater improvisation. Spoken language and improvisation have a fluidity that is perhaps not dissimilar to a computers ability to endlessly manipulate binary information.

To help develop this way of working I have studied a number of styles of music where rhythms appear to be able to be remembered and manipulated with ease and at speeds that are baffling to those not familiar with the music.

The musical styles that I have studied so far have included Cuban Rumba and Bata, Flamenco and Konnakol. These rich artforms all require many lifetimes of study

which would be impossible for me to give so I have approached them as an enthusiastic amateur. I have been fortunate to study with some of the most incredible performers in their respective genres. Musicians who have the ability to improvise and manipulate rhythms within their genre with incredible ease. This has included the Flamenco Guitarist Jose Manuel Leon and Rumbero Yovanni Diaz Herrera.

From studying both Flamenco and AfroCuban Music with the performers mentioned it is clear that they share an intimate knowledge of the rhythmic framework used to to transmit the musical information. These tend to be strict accents on beats within a cycle that Flamenco artists would call this Compas and Rumberos Clave. These rhythmic templates are often absorbed from childhood and are so ingrained in the performer they are said to be internalised. These rhythmic templates are so important to the music they should be studied well before trying more elaborate patterns. We could approach our serial data in a similar way.

Figure 4. binary representation of hello world

If we return to the ‘hello world’ example and look at it in its binary form we notice that each lower case ASCII letter contains a shared rhythm. Each 10 bits of information always begin with a start bit of 0 and end with a 1, and the 7th and 8th bits are always 1. Whilst trying to get used to performing these letters I found it useful to consider this shared rhythm as a kind of the clave or compas of serial ASCII.

Another feature of the music studied is the common use of a combination of hand movements and memonics to vocalise the rhythms. This type of vocalisation of rhythm has been described by Michael Atherton as “rhythm-speak” and is described in his paper RHYTHM-SPEAK: MNEMONIC, LANGUAGE PLAY OR SONG?. [7] It is shared by many forms of music. I found that adopting ideas from this was a useful way to learn the letters. Through some practice I can now comfortably do this at around 120 bpm

	1	2	3	4	5	
h			Ta	Ta	Ka	Ka
e		Ka	Ka	Ta	Ka	Ka
l			Ka	Ta	Ta	Ka
l			Ka	Ta	Ta	Ka
o		Ka	Ta	Ka	Ta	Ka

Figure 5. Konnakol representation of hello

I used a technique common to the South Indian vocal music Konnakol of tapping individual fingers of the right hand on the palm of the left and singing syllables Ta or Ka. I found that breaking the patterns down like this gave me a much more manageable way to navigate the 10 beat cycle and in particular help internalise the rhythmic template or clave discussed above. This is helped by being able to associate certain sounds with certain fingers.

5. PERFORMING THE SYSTEM

Performing in front of an audience tests both the nerves of the performer and the robustness of the technology used. It is also a good way to gauge if the audience understand the translation processes taking place. During a performance of the piece at DIEM Aarhus [8], I chose not to explain what I was about to do and to describe the work only through performing with it. Using the software projected behind me and singing in binary I said hello and described myself as a signal in a noisy channel. Through some laughter within the audience it was clear that after producing several letters that there was some understanding of what I was doing. It was also clear that mistakes I made and my ability to delete them by using a binary version of back spaces was as engaging to the audience as producing text.

One feature of the system is that the audience represents the noise within the system. There is always the potential for people to override the signal I produce. However, per-

haps due to politeness or lack of understanding it has not yet happened.

Figure 6. Performing the piece How we communicate at Dansk Institut for Elektronisk Musik

6. CONCLUSION

I have provided some background to the idea of exploring the structure of high speed data transmission by developing technology that allows it to be slowed down and performed within the realm of human performed music. I have provided a brief background to listening to information and have given examples of how learning other styles of improvised music could be beneficial in attempting to communicate with computers in their native binary language.

There are many possible directions for this work to be taken forward. First would be to make the system robust enough and simple enough to use to allow other musicians from a wide range of backgrounds to explore it. This would allow further exploration of the musical potential of these unusual patterns to take place.

The approach taken in this research could of course be developed to incorporate a much wider range of data transmission protocols and multiple performers. This would allow the enormous complexity and diversity of digital communication systems. Increases in complexity would be likely to have a negative impact on an audience’s ability to understand what is happening in the work and would be no doubt harder for musicians to perform. However as described earlier there are plenty of instances in musical history where dense complexity has been favoured over simplification.

7. REFERENCES

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